

Action, self-consciousness, and outgroup demarcation: A reply to the commentaries

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I am indebted and grateful to all the commentators for their insightful contributions. I find myself agreeing with a good deal of their responses, and even those I don't agree with have provided me with a productive opportunity to further refine and clarify my view. Let me also express a special word of gratitude to Andrew Inkpin and Marilyn Stendera for inviting me to contribute with the lead article and for managing the whole process in such a constructive manner.

“I, You, and We: Beyond Individualism and Collectivism” can to some extent be seen as a precis of a book that was yet to be written. Since submitting the lead article, I have managed to finish the book in question, which in addition to offering more extensive analyses of all the themes briefly addressed in the article also covers many additional topics (Zahavi 2025).

The primacy of action

Let me start with a *mea culpa* that relates to a critical point made by Arto Laitinen. Laitinen faults me for having strawmanned the existing analytic discussion of collective intentionality by claiming that it only focuses on joint action. As Laitinen rightly points out this is a very uncharitable (and ultimately completely indefensible) claim, since the analytic discussion is far more multifaceted. My intention, however, was never to suggest that philosophers such as Bratman, Gilbert, Searle and Tuomela have only worked on joint action. What I meant to say was that these philosophers tend to take joint action as the point of departure for their analysis of collective intentionality. And as I see it, this has not only led them to focus less on questions pertaining to the relation between collective identity and selfhood on the one hand and collective intentionality and social cognition on the other when compared to the phenomenologists I have been working on, it has also had implications for how they have approached other types of collective intentionality. As an example of the former, it is well and good to concede that we-intentionality requires some capacity for social cognition, some “sense of the other person as a candidate for shared intentionality” (Searle 1990: 415) and “some direct or indirect communication (or signaling) between the participants” (Tuomela 2007: 87). But this still leaves it an open question whether all types of social cognition, including empathy, second-person engagement, imaginative perspective taking, and inferential mindreading are all

equally conducive to the emergence of a we-perspective. Phenomenology has more to offer regarding such a question than what we find in Searle and Tuomela. As for the latter point, Gilbert can serve as an example. As much as I have profited from her rich and insightful work, I do find the exemplary role she ascribes to action striking. As she writes in *Joint Commitment*, by analysing joint action her aim is to offer an adequate account “that provides individually necessary and jointly sufficient conditions on shared intention” (Gilbert 2014a: 105). She consequently takes her analysis of joint action to be of pertinence for an understanding of other forms of collective intentionality as well. Indeed, for Gilbert, different types of psychological states, such as believing, intending, and feeling something together can all be construed as cases of “doing something together” (Gilbert 2014a: 32-33). In contrast to Tuomela, who in *Philosophy of Sociality* explicitly states that he will not discuss collective emotions (2007: 65), Gilbert does in fact address that topic, but her analysis is clearly indebted to the account of joint commitment that she developed in her work on collective action: “Persons X, Y, and so on, are collectively excited if and only if they are jointly committed to be excited as a body” (Gilbert 2014b: 23).

Some collective emotions do involve joint commitments. The appropriateness of rebukes and apologies can serve as evidence for the presence of such commitments. But there are many cases of collective emotions – including cases of collective enjoyment or collective fear – where such rebukes and apologies make little sense. This is incidentally something that Bratman has also commented upon. As an objection to Gilbert’s claim that joint commitments are necessary for collective intentionality, Bratman mentions a situation where two people “more or less spontaneously applaud in response to an obviously outstanding performance” (Bratman 2009: 151). As Bratman then observes, “if one of the participants in these shared activities opted out without warning, the other might well be justifiably surprised. But it is one thing to falsify a prior expectation, another to violate a prior entitlement” (Bratman 2009: 152). It is hard not to agree with this observation, although one could then add that Bratman’s own preoccupation with and analysis of complex cooperative activities is also not well suited to handle such cases of spontaneously shared emotions. We can act and do things together, but it is not obvious that the awe felt and shared by a group of tourists who visits a pharaonic tomb can or should be analysed in the same way as, say, a heist that a group of criminals carefully plan and execute together.

When I in my lead article argued that a thorough examination of collective intentionality must also attend to experience, engage with topics related to self- and group-identity, and reflect on the nature of interpersonal understanding, I was not claiming that an

examination of collective intentionality that doesn't do so is futile or mistaken, but merely that it will be limited and partial. Nor did I want to suggest that the inclusion of these topics must involve a commitment to a quite specific account of selfhood and social cognition. I have my own take on these matters, and my aim in the lead article was to showcase some of the analyses that phenomenology has to offer. But there are of course other approaches possible, and my more principled point was simply that these are topics that shouldn't be ignored.

Elisabeth Pacherie and I both agree that the prospects of building a general theory of collective intentionality by extrapolating from analyses of joint action are dim since such an approach underestimates the diverse forms of collective intentionality. One problem with such an approach, which I will return to later, is that it by focusing on small-scale agency risks losing sight of the wide range of social structures that are essential for many large-scale collective actions. Another problem is that it by often focusing on sophisticated types of cooperative activities, i.e., activities with complex goals that require prior planning and various coordinating and organizing roles (Bratman 2009: 153), fail to account for more elementary forms of collective intentionality. As just pointed out, some shared emotions are importantly different from carefully planned actions, but consider also, say, a coordinated dyadic interaction such as a game of peekaboo which is something the child can participate in together with the adult, even though the child lacks advanced reasoning capacities and higher-order theory of mind abilities (see also Pacherie 2014).

In her discussion of some of the more basic structures, Pacherie mentions the role of both interpersonal entrainment and joint attention. Let me add a few comments that relate these topics to older work in phenomenology.

There is currently ample empirical evidence in support of the idea that emotional integration and interpersonal identification can be facilitated by low-level processes of bodily synchronization and attunement. But there is a difference between facilitating something and playing a necessary and/or sufficient role. In classical phenomenology, thinkers like Stein and Walther have both insisted on the difference between processes of contagion and mimicry and collective forms of intentionality, including forms of experiential sharing. Whereas Stein concedes that processes of contagion (or alignment or attunement) can make people's behavior converge, she disputes that this in and of itself makes them experience anything in common (Stein 2000: 241). This verdict is echoed by Walther, who also argues that whereas processes of contagion and mimicry can affect my own experience, this will not in and of itself lead to any form of experiential sharing (although it might facilitate it). For an experience or intention to be shared, the experience or intention should be felt as *our*, as co-owned, as one *we* are

having or entertaining (Walther 1923: 75), and for that to happen something over and beyond contagion or alignment is required. It will also involve an incorporation of the other's perspective. As I read Pacherie, she would endorse an account along these lines, and also Stavenhagen's assertion that the property of us-ness ("Unserigkeit") is part of the phenomenal character of a shared experience (Stavenhagen 1933: 38), since Pacherie also writes that shared experiences include not only a retained for-me-ness, but also a sense of togetherness.

But how is the basic sense of togetherness established, and how do the involved participants know that they have obtained contact with each other? In an article from 2019, Siposova and Carpenter introduced distinctions between monitoring attention, common attention, mutual attention, and shared attention that Pacherie also picks up on. In her commentary, Pacherie discusses these distinctions, so I will not repeat them here, except in order to say that one can find almost the same analysis in Husserl (see Zahavi 2023). The main difference between Siposova and Carpenter on the one hand and Husserl on the other is that although Siposova and Carpenter concede that mutual attention doesn't involve any intentional bidirectional communicative exchange (Siposova & Carpenter 2019: 263), they still claim that it qualifies as second personal (2019: 271), whereas Husserl would want to reserve the label second-personal for communicative exchanges. On his account, the I-you relation requires more than simply reciprocal perceptual contact. What is also needed is mutual address and communication, where the latter is understood not as a simple transmission of information, but as a kind of communion. Metaphorically speaking, whereas reciprocal perceptual contact (mutual attention) allows two subjects to be "for-one-another", the I-you relation is more demanding in that it requires the subjects to be intentionally "within-each-other" (*Ineinander*) (Husserl 1973c: 477). On Husserl's account, it is the process of mutual address, of uptake, acknowledgment, and reply, that allows the subjects to become intentionally intertwined and interlocked.

You and we

One of the claims I make in the lead article is that second-person engagement (or shared attention, to use Siposova and Carpenter's terminology) is crucial for the intentional intertwining we find in a we-perspective. Importantly, this is not meant to suggest that one can only constitute a we together with people one has engaged second-personally with. The claim is rather that the most basic kind of we is the one that is established dyadically, and that the capacity to participate in other (larger and more anonymous) forms of we is made possible

by some of the cognitive and affective modulations occasioned by second-person engagement. Let me incidentally also make it clear that I, in contrast to what Husserl seems to be claiming, don't think every I-you relation already amounts to a we-formation.

In her commentary, Sarah Pawlett Jackson discusses what she takes to be an ambiguity in my elaboration of the relationship between the second-person singular and the first-person plural perspective. For Pawlett Jackson, one important difference between relating to another as a you, and relating with another as a we, is that whereas the former is dyadic and frontal, the latter is triadic and sideways (or horizontal), or to put differently, whereas I am focusing on the other in the former case, both of us are jointly focusing on the world in the latter. Given this rendering, Pawlett Jackson then suggests that there are two different ways of understanding the claim that the first-person plural is founded on the second-person singular perspective. Either it can mean that the capacity for second-person engagement is required for the capacity for we-relations and that the former therefore has developmental and empirical priority, or it can mean that the second-person perspective is a structural or constitutive part of the we, and that it therefore has ontological priority. Ultimately, Pawlett Jackson opts for the former claim, and her conclusion is that it might be better to say that both perspectives (second-person singular and first-person plural) are structurally dependent upon reciprocal empathy. She ends her commentary by suggesting that more ongoing work on more complex forms of first-person plural and second-person singular perspectives are needed. I wholeheartedly agree with the latter point and would like to use the occasion to recommend Pawlett Jackson's own existing writings on the topic (e.g., Pawlett Jackson 2020, 2021). The questions she raises are important, but let me voice a few concerns I have about the way she is presenting the options. Is it really true that the I-you relation is frontal and dyadic, and that it cannot be triadic? I am not convinced. Two people who are communicatively connected are typically communicating about something. If I address you with a request and ask you to clean the dishes and you respond with a denial, we are standing in an I-you relationship, but it is not a relationship that takes place in a vacuum. We always understand each other as related to one and the same world. What then about the we-perspective? Does it lack second-personal relations between the participants? I don't think it necessarily does. Here is one way to think of the difference between relating to another from a third-person and from a second-person perspective. In the former case, you intend a particular kind of object, a minded one. In the latter case, you relate to a co-subject. Is it not the latter kind of awareness that is required if you want to constitute a we with somebody else? Take the case of dancing together. Presumably that is an activity that *we* are doing together. Even if we don't speak to each other, our bodies communicate with each

other, and there is a constant forth and back of address and response. Rather than arguing that the I-you relation is always dyadic, it might be better to acknowledge that there are different types of you awareness, some focal and others more peripheral.

Phenomenology and analytic philosophy

In his commentary, Laitinen discusses the difference between the phenomenological focus on experience and the focus on a rational point of view that we find in Gilbert, Rovane, and Petit. One of the outcomes of this comparison is that a group on the latter account might be said to have a point of view and might be committed to something as a group that differs from what any of the individuals that compose it might commit to qua individuals. Laitinen then asks whether the phenomenological tradition also offers comparable discussions of a normative group perspective.

One initially point to make is that phenomenologists would typically question any straightforward experience/reason divide (see e.g., Husserl 1975). But when it comes to the more specific question, we do, in fact, find related considerations in Husserl, who, for instance, writes of a personality of higher order “in which lives a will, a purpose, an embodiment of practical convictions, political or scientific” (Husserl 1973b: 90). How should one understand such claims? When Husserl writes that “As an individual subject has its private convictions, its private views, evaluations, volitions, so an organisation, e.g., a club, a parliament, a faculty etc., has its joint convictions, views, resolutions, commands, wishes etc. On both sides there are momentary acts as well as permanent habitual act directions” (Husserl 2002: 135), his rejection of methodological individualism is straightforward. But while denying that the intentional achievements of the group can be understood as a mere aggregation of individual achievements, Husserl also repeatedly talks of this communal spirit as a “many-headed subjectivity” (Husserl 1973b: 218). This is a significant qualifier. The personality of higher order, and the we it instantiates, is not a large scale I, but a plural subject. It is composed of a plurality of members, each with their own stream of consciousness. There is never any fusional unification. As Husserl also writes, the higher order personality is “a communicative unity” founded on multiplicities; its substrate is none other than the “communicative multiplicity of persons” (Husserl 1973b: 200-201).

This is only the beginning of the analysis, however, since Husserl would readily recognize that we as individuals are formed by our socialization and enculturation, and that the contribution of past group members remain part of the background of our common life and

provides the group with a distinct communal style encompassing shared conventions, practices, and beliefs. Whereas shared norms and customs might be of lesser importance for short-lived intentional intertwinements, they are crucial for more enduring group formations, and to self-identify as a group member will in many instances also be a question of considering certain group norms as binding. In some cases, this might even involve endorsing views or pursuing goals that would conflict with one's own privately held goals and interest. One problem with Husserl's account, however, is that he tends to use the notion of personality of higher order not only as the label for a family or a tightly knit group of collaborators (mathematicians working jointly on a problem), but also to refer to large scale group formations such as a city or a nation state. To do the latter is, however, to assign far too much unity and conformity to such formations. It fails to recognize to what extent real communities always harbour diversity and debates. That one can find discussions in phenomenology that targets questions of normative group cohesion is, however, clear.

The issue of unity and diversity brings me to a point brought up by both Laitinen and Avramides, namely my assessment of Mead. In my text, I claimed that Meadean social constructivism doesn't merely fail to account for experiential subjectivity, but also for genuine communal life (for a more extensive discussion see Zahavi & Zelinsky 2024). Why make the latter claim? Because I think that communal life and we-experiences are forms of intersubjectivity and that a proper account of the latter must factor in real difference. To repeat the point made earlier, a we is no large scale I. A we is a plural perspective, and even if members of a we must be bound together in some fashion, even if the togetherness and being-with-one-another distinctive of a we requires some kind of integration, it cannot be one that erases or negates difference, in favor of unity and fusion. It is precisely because we have underived perspectives of our own, it is precisely because my perspective on matter is not simply constituted by others (and vice versa), that agreement and collaboration as well as conflict and disagreement is possible. As Laitinen has also argued, some ontological independence must be preserved (Laitinen 2014: 216).

The question is whether Mead's social constructivism according to which you become a self by internalizing the other's perspective can allow for such independence. Avramides suggests that one can defend Mead here. After all, Mead doesn't merely argue that the self is socially determined and constituted, he also speaks of the presence of an 'I'. As Avramides asks, is that not sufficient for underived plurality. I don't think so. If we go to *Mind, Self and Society*, it is true that Mead complicates his account by arguing that the socially constituted self involves *two* distinguishable phases, the 'I' and the 'me' (Mead 1962: 178). As is clear

from his discussion, however, the 'I' is never given any real independency. Rather, for Mead, the 'I' is the phase of self that "reacts to the self which arises through taking the attitudes of others. Through taking these attitudes we have introduced the 'me' and we react to it as an 'I'" (Mead 1962: 174). The 'I' consequently corresponds to a retrospective reflection on how we inhabit the social roles that we have acquired through socialization.

In *After Virtue*, MacIntyre argued that "the individual is identified and constituted in and through certain of his or her roles." And as MacIntyre then added, "There is no 'I' apart from these" roles (MacIntyre 1981: 172). But to identify an individual completely with his socially assigned typifications, to apprehend him as nothing but his social roles, is, as Berger and Luckmann have convincingly argued, nothing but an instance of radical reification (Berger & Luckmann 1991: 108).

Avramides doesn't find it evident why communal being-together should go hand in hand with unbridgeable separation. But to talk of the latter in this context is simply to ward off any fusional account, i.e., the idea that distinct streams of phenomenal consciousnesses might coalesce and become one. Ruling this possibility out is not meant to jeopardize the possibility of a real community; quite to the contrary. To put it differently, if one denies what might be called perspectival autonomy, there is a price to pay. If you deny perspectival autonomy, if you deprive the self of any kind of independence, you must also deny the transcendence of the you and the otherness of the other. And absent both, any reference to a rich communal life is deprived of meaning.

At one point in his commentary, Laitinen remarks that more or less everyone in the collective intentionality debate would agree with Husserl that "the radical and underived individuation of consciousness prohibits any fusion between streams of consciousness". I agree, and I also suspect that most of them would have far less of an issue with my notion of for-me-ness and minimal experiential selfhood than Avramides. Contrary to what she seems to be suggesting, the latter notions are not so deeply embedded in phenomenological theorizing that they will be quite controversial to anybody from outside of that tradition. Both notions can also be found in works by contemporary analytic philosophers. Here is, for instance, what Horgan and Nichols (whose credentials as analytic philosophers I assume nobody would dispute) write:

Phenomenal subjectivity [...] is the 'for me' aspect of phenomenal consciousness; there can be no occurrent 'what-it-is-like-ness' apart from an experiential subject *for whom* there is something that a token phenomenal state is like. Moreover, in phenomenally

conscious experience, the experiencing self is not just *instantiating* the pertinent phenomenal state/process. Rather, the experiencing self is *experientially present* within the state/process, and is present in a quite direct and intimate way. [...] Phenomenal subjectivity—the ‘for-me-ness’ of phenomenal consciousness without which one could not instantiate states with phenomenal character (i.e., with ‘what-it’s-like-ness’), is an experientially *direct* way in which the self is present in phenomenal consciousness (Horgan & Nichols 2016: 146).

I fear that Avramides might be operating with a too monolithic conception of what analytic philosophy amounts to and I don’t quite understand how she can write that “analytic philosophers do not share Stein’s concern to understand the structure of experience. One thing that concerns them is how we might think of the mind in relation to the body/brain, and many will hold to some form of reduction here.” Not only is reductionism not as popular today as it was 30 years ago, which is one reason why illusionism and panpsychism have gained in popularity, but even more importantly, a lot of very interesting work by analytic philosopher does focus on trying to understand the structure of experience. Apart from Horgan and Nichols, one could also mention Kriegel, Dainton, Strawson, Siewert, Montague, Farkas and many others.

Part of my aim has been to contribute to the dialogue between the analytic discussions and the phenomenological tradition. I have in the past profited from Laitinen’s own efforts to bring insights from classical recognition theory to bear on the contemporary discussion of collective intentionality. On Laitinen’s reading, Hegel distinguishes as least four aspects of selfhood, namely sentience, intentionality, self-consciousness, and social identity. For Hegel, the latter two depend upon recognition from others. Laitinen’s final question is whether such a view represents a marked rupture with the position of the phenomenologists or whether there might be ways of making them compatible. It depends. Phenomenologists would typically draw somewhat different distinctions. Consider, for instance, the case of self-consciousness. One of the well-known contributions found in phenomenology is the distinction between not only pre-reflective and reflective self-consciousness, but also between different types of reflective self-consciousness. Whereas most of the phenomenologists would argue that pre-reflective self-consciousness in its most fundamental form isn’t dependent upon social interaction or recognition, but rather to be thought of as an intrinsic feature of consciousness – as Ingarden writes, the original mode of being of conscious life is to be in the form of being self-conscious; in the absence of such self-consciousness, an experience would not be an experience (Ingarden

1992: 156), i.e. a phenomenally conscious process – and therefore ultimately also a precondition for any experience of recognizing or being recognized, there are other forms of self-consciousness that are socially mediated. As Husserl writes, I come to be a “personal subject, come to attain personal ‘self-consciousness’, in the I-you relation” (Husserl 1973b: 171).

Avramides asks whether I take social and cultural factors to be essential for the development of selfhood and personhood. I certainly do. In fact, I don’t think one can understand what is distinctive of human selfhood independently of social and cultural factors. I would consequently not claim that the social is only contingently required for self-development, and hopefully that should also make it clear why I don’t endorse individualism. On my view, group membership involves a transformation of the human individual. And in so far as individuals are changed psychologically in group settings, we need to explore the group if we are to fully understand the psychology of the individual. I take that to be incompatible with individualism, if that is understood as the view that social groups are nothing over and above the (pre-social) individuals who compose them.

The contribution of French phenomenology

In her contribution, Sara Heinämaa points to the existence of resources in postwar French phenomenology that I didn’t draw upon in my article (and which also play a relatively minor role in my book); resources that, as she rightly argues, complements the contributions of the early German phenomenologists. There are many ways to characterize the difference between the German and the French phenomenologists, but an obvious one concerns the changed historical and political situation. Husserl’s analysis of consciousness was initially very generic. It was a matter of investigating what characterizes consciousness as such. In the later phase of his work, Husserl became increasingly interested in the question of how cultural, historical, and developmental conditions affect our consciousness and understanding. It is this movement from the universal towards the concrete, empirical, and historical that is intensified in the work of the postwar French phenomenologists. Already Sartre’s and Merleau-Ponty’s early work drew inspiration from and engaged with empirical psychology and neuroscience. In 1949 Simone de Beauvoir published her major work *Le deuxième sexe*, which contained a phenomenological account of the gendered body, and in 1952 the psychiatrist and philosopher Frantz Fanon published *Peau noire, masques blancs*, which criticised French colonialism and racism and offered a phenomenological analysis of the racialised body. Not surprisingly such

a focus also affected the way these thinkers approached questions pertaining to collective intentionality and communal experiences.

As Heinämaa points out, when discussing social formations, one cannot merely focus on dyads and triads, one must also consider far more institutionally embedded group formations. Some of these connect members in a non-reciprocal manner. The most obvious case being transgenerational communities, where the contributions and accomplishments of past members affect the lives of contemporary members without the reverse holding true. This is, however, an insight that can already be found in classical phenomenology. Husserl, for instance, recognizes that the temporal cohesion of some groups is based not only on personal interaction, but also on shared culture and common history. When an individual performs various intentional acts, these acts leave traces and might create lasting tendencies. Likewise, what we do together remain in the background of our common life. Current members will be influenced by the past achievements and the common values that more or less deliberately have been endorsed and promoted by past members (Husserl 1973a: 108, 1973b: 220). Husserl would consequently speak of a habituated sociality that contributes to the constitution of a distinct communal style encompassing shared conventions, practices, and beliefs.

But again, it is important to recognize the existence of different types of groups, and – as also pointed out by Pacherie – not to seek to account for the constitution of them all in the same manner. There are groups that exist in order to get things done, and groups that seek to maintain their own continued existence. There are groups that come into being as a result of a declaration, and groups that are only established as a result of years of living together. There are groups that possess an organized structure and groups based simply on shared features. The membership criteria for each of these group-formations differ. Groups can vary in terms of their size, duration, task-orientation, and organization, but also in terms of their *entitativity*, i.e., the extent to which they are viewed by others (and/or by their own members) as possessing real unity and coherence (Lickel et al. 2000: 224). Why are members of a military platoon, for instance, more likely to be seen as a real group than people sitting close to each other in a cafeteria, and why are members of the former more likely to think of themselves as part of a we, than the latter?

Heinämaa discusses Sartre's example of people waiting for a bus. Rather than coming together as a result of communicatively shared plans or intentions, it is the shared context that is the decisive trigger. But I think it is important not to forget that a we is a plural subject. For some groups, membership can be determined based on the presence of a certain set of objective features. Whether or not you belong to blood group A, B, AB, or O is determined by the genes

you inherit from your parents. Other groups such as social class or ethnicity might be defined by less objective criteria, but you might still be counted as a member by others regardless of your own view of the matter. In all these cases, membership can be externally assigned regardless of whether you know or care about it and can happen even if you actively disidentify with the group in question. Such externally enforced classifications are, however, not of much relevance when it comes to understanding we-relationships. The latter is not an externally observed entity, but something experienced from within, something involving plural self-consciousness, i.e., something involving a (pre-reflective or reflective) awareness of oneself as member or participant of a we (Schmid 2014). In contrast to various kinds of objectively defined groups, membership of a we requires an experiential anchoring. To be part of a we, is to be with and relate to other members in a distinct way; one involving participation and identification. A multitude of factors can trigger or prompt such identification. Belonging to the same social category (being Danish, from Copenhagen, being an academic etc.) can help. Sharing a common fate – waiting on a much-delayed bus, being stuck in a lifeboat with other survivors, or witnessing a traffic accident – might also make the emergence of a we-perspective more likely. But what must be emphasized is that none of these factors are sufficient in themselves. If you do not self-identify as a member of the relevant group (which is something that can happen pre-reflectively), you are not part of that we. To put it differently, when adopting a we-perspective, you are precisely adopting a *first-person* plural perspective, you are not leaving the first-person point of view behind (Carr 1986: 530).

Heinämaa also reminds us of the way in which worldly objects might facilitate and motivate joint actions and collective forms of intentionality. Although this point was much more forcefully developed by Sartre and Beauvoir than by Husserl, the latter was not oblivious to the role of the world. As Husserl would argue, even if there are forms of face-to-face engagements, where the experiential states of two subjects are tightly coordinated and calibrated, we shouldn't forget the world we are situated in. After all, the interplay of address and response (which can be pre-linguistic) doesn't merely produce a communicative connection between the speakers, but at the same time, as Husserl puts it, "a unitary relation of them to a common surrounding world" (Husserl 1989a: 203). I am not only aware of myself as situated in a world, I am aware of myself as situated in a world that I share with others. Indeed, when understanding others, we always understand them as related to the same world as ourselves, to a common "earth and sky" (Husserl 1989a: 201). And as Husserl then continues,

We are in a relation to a common surrounding world – we are in a personal association: these belong together. We could not be persons for others if a common surrounding world did not stand there for us in a community, in an intentional linkage of our lives. Correlatively spoken, the one is constituted essentially with the other (Husserl 1989a: 201).

The point, however, is not simply that communication often concerns worldly matters of shared interest, and that second-person relations to shared objects allow for richer and more complex forms of interaction insofar as a sustained focus on a shared external object or project provides “both an anchor and a pivot for the intentional relations of both interactive partners to interconnect” (Moore and Baressi 2017: 9). Husserl is also arguing that communication affects how the world shows up. To use a classical example, looking at a whipsaw on one’s own and looking at a whipsaw together with a co-worker are two very different matters. Whereas the whipsaw in the first instance will look unwieldy, it will in the second show up as something that affords possibilities of interaction for you as a unit. When you perceive something together with another, the structure of the perceptual field will be re-organized accordingly. Importantly, the relation between co-attenders and the world is not unidirectional. Although the social and cultural world is constituted by a multiplicity of communicating subjects, the world thus constituted also allows for new forms of communication, socialization, and cultural production. Most concrete encounters will never start from scratch but always be influenced by already available cultural-historical communal accomplishments.

The first-person perspective

In his commentary, Varun Ravikumar mainly pursues two aims. On the one hand, he wants to argue that Bourdieu offers us important insights regarding the relationship between the individual and the social. On the other hand, he also makes the more specific claim that Bourdieu, in his elaboration of the role of habitus, is able to offer a social constructivist account of the first-person perspective and of the mineness of experience. I don’t have any problems with the former aim and claim. I think an exhaustive account of sociality and of the relation between self and group will call for and require various complementary perspectives and approaches, and I am confident that Bourdieu’s work can make an important contribution. By contrast, I find the second claim quite unpersuasive.

I have criticized different forms of social constructivism over the years (e.g., Zahavi 2022, Zahavi & Zelinsky 2023), and one of my repeated criticisms has been that defenders of social constructivism often conflate different agendas. I also think that conflation is present in Ravikumar's comment. Ravikumar writes that our exposure to the social environment provides us with a practical knowledge that can make us anticipate certain potentialities of action, and that the "bodily subject's practical knowledge of their everyday social surroundings is underpinned by their habitus." I think this is correct, and not very far removed from what classical phenomenology would argue. The question is how and why this is supposed to elucidate the mineness of experience (a notion I incidentally do not use in the lead article). Drawing repeatedly on an article by Slors and Jongepier, Ravikumar claims that practical encounters with varying social situations provides the bodily subject with diachronic and synchronic habits, dispositions, and skills and that the mineness of experience is the systematic coherence of these acquisitions. But this has nothing to do with the mineness I have discussed in previous writings or the notion of experiential subjectivity I allude to in my lead article. The latter notion is primarily meant to capture the first-personal character of experience, the fact that our experiences in virtue of being the phenomenally conscious episode they are, are also epistemically presented to us in a way that differs from the way in which they are available and accessible to others. If Ravikumar would maintain that habitus can account for and explain the first-person perspective, he doesn't provide any arguments for the claim.

One question raised by Heinämaa concerns my precise understanding of perspectives. Are perspectives (say, the first-person, second-person or third-person singular or the first-person plural perspective) features that belong inherently and intrinsically to subjects or are they rather attitudes that subjects can adopt and switch between? As Heinämaa rightly points out, different passages in my article can be read in support of either possibility. This is no coincidence, however, since my claim would be that perspectives can be both, and that it depends on which perspectives we are talking about. The first-person singular perspective is on my account an intrinsic feature of conscious life; the second-person singular and the first-person plural perspective by contrast are not intrinsic to consciousness but are perspectives that can emerge if certain conditions are fulfilled (Zahavi 2023). Importantly, even when adopting a first-person plural perspective, or a third-person singular perspective, the first-person singular perspective is not negated or abolished, but remains in force as an experiential condition of possibility for the other perspectives. To complicate matters, however, one can also make a distinction between the perspectives as they are pre-reflectively lived through, and the perspectives as they are reflectively articulated. As a consequence, and this was for instance

highlighted by Sartre in a famous example from *L'être et le néant*, one can approach one and the same first-person experience from a variety of different adopted perspectives. One can thematize an ongoing pain in a manner that tries to stay true to its first-personal character, but one can also objectify the very same pain and, for instance, classify and describe it using medical terminology (Sartre 2003: 380).

Heinämaa also asks whether the notion of perspective should be understood in such a way that it retains its spatial and coordinational connotations, or whether the notion is rather to be understood metaphorically. As much as I would endorse the idea that a perspective is an embodied perspective, I am critical of the attempt to offer a spatial interpretation, which often goes hand in hand with a reductionist agenda. Olaf Blanke and Thomas Metzinger, for instance, have argued that a weak first-person perspective is “a purely geometrical feature” of our visuospatial presentation of reality. When we perceive objects, we see objects as being to the right or left, further away or closer by. On this account, the weak first-person perspective is simply the zero-point of projection that functions as the geometrical origin of the seeing organism’s embodied perspective (Blanke and Metzinger 2009). In a somewhat similar manner, Dainton has tried to explain the perspectival character of experience by appealing to a spatial framework. The reason the tree you perceive is presented to you in a perspectival manner is because you yourself are given with a determinate spatial location (Dainton 2016).

Whereas I do think that an analysis of perceptual experience must factor in the spatiality of our own body, I do not think the proposals in question manage to capture or elucidate that which makes a perspective a *first-person* perspective, namely its subjective character. Having a first-person perspective on something is not simply a question of standing at a certain angle and a certain distance from the object in question. It is also a question of subjectively experiencing the object in a certain way. But the spatial construal does nothing to elucidate this feature. Furthermore, it is not clear how a reference to spatial coordinates would allow one to account for the indisputable first-personal character of emotions such as joy, shame, anger, or despair.

The role of the outgroup

In his comments, Yoann Malinge raises some interesting points, one of them being that one’s identity can be influenced not only by the groups of which one is a member, but also by the groups that exclude one. I agree. The idea that the very exclusion of and by other(s) can serve a unificatory aim resonates with ideas found in social psychology. If I am confronted with 10

pears on a plate, I might notice their individual differences. If I am confronted with 10 pears on one plate and 10 oranges on another plate, the difference between the two types of fruits will tend to overshadow any difference there might be between the individual pears. One can observe somewhat similar processes in the social domain. The widespread use of social categorization and typification means that individual members will not primarily be seen as unique individuals but as representative group members. They will be assigned all the characteristics of their respective group, which will lead not only to an exaggeration of the unity, coherence, and homogeneity of both in-group members and out-group members respectively but also to an overestimation of intergroup differences (Hogg and Abrams 1998: 19). The encounter with an outgroup can consequently not only make one's own ingroup membership salient, but the mentioned accentuation effect will also facilitate a further consolidation and reification of one's group identity.

Malinge also makes a number of additional claims. He writes for instance that “before considering oneself as a member of a group, one person can identify themselves as excluded from another group. Before a relation between ‘We and you’, there is a relation of exclusion between ‘Them and I’ that is difficult to overcome.” If this is meant to highlight the fact that one can be assigned a group-identity by others, and that such an externally enforced classification might impact one's self-understanding and even interfere with one's ability to form groups of one's own, then I would, of course, agree, though I would still insist that an externally enforced group-identity only amounts to a *we*-identity if it is appropriated and endorsed. But if the claim is that one has to be excluded from one group before one can identify with another, I fail to see the argument. Malinge also argues, drawing extensively on Sartre, that if several people are ostracized for the same reason (their ethnicity, their sexuality, their religious beliefs) then they can only identify with each other if they decide to act together. Again, I don't really understand the argument.

In her commentary, Heinämaa raises somewhat similar considerations. As she points out, for Sartre, the role of outside observers is not only about solidifying or strengthening a group formation that has already been constituted on other grounds. No, it is more fundamental, in that it is the outsider who allows for the very establishment of the group as a self-conscious social formation, one that can perform collective actions. If this is intended as a general claim about groups, I find Sartre's position unconvincing. Sartre's reasoning is connected to claims specific to his philosophical position, but the general idea, that boundary demarcations vis-à-vis others are essential to group formations, is widespread. Thus, we find Hylland Eriksen argue that “group identities must always be defined in relation to what they are not – in other words,

in relation to non-members of the group” (Hylland Eriksen 2010: 14), and Young claim that “groups are an expression of social relations; a group exists only in relation to at least one other group” (Young 1990: 43). But even if groups have non-members, this will in many cases be a consequence of, and not a precondition for, the identity of the group. What members of groups have in common, what brings them together, is not always their perceived difference to other groups. Sharing a common fate and having similar interests can also give rise to a sense of togetherness. Four individuals might move a heavy wardrobe up a staircase. They are clearly doing this together, and their capacity to do so and to experience the joint action from a first-person plural perspective is not dependent upon any outgroup demarcation. I might hike through the night in order to reach a mountain summit in time for the sunrise. When I reach my destination, I realize that another hiker has made her way to the summit from the other side. Standing side by side, we enjoy the sunrise together. What we experience is different from what we would have experienced had each of us been alone. It is a shared experience. But the sharing of the experience, the fact that it qualifies as an experience *we* are having together, is not conditioned upon us demarcating ourselves from all the people who failed to go on the hike and remained asleep (even if thinking about the latter might add to the quality of the shared experience).

Denying that a boundary demarcation vis-à-vis others is essential for all group formation doesn't entail, however, that such a demarcation cannot be transformative, by thematizing, accentuating or consolidating the group identity. Nor does it rule out that a demarcation vis-à-vis outgroups might be essential to some very important types of groups. One likely candidate would be national communities. To forge a national identity, an identity spanning local differences and bridging spatial and temporal distances, other requirements are needed than when it comes to the constitution of dyads, triads, or local communities. One powerful unifying force can precisely be the presence of outsiders. To quote Hylland Eriksen again, “ethnicity is an aspect of social relationship between persons who consider themselves as essentially distinctive from members of other groups of whom they are aware and with whom they enter into relationships” (Hylland Eriksen 2010: 16-17). On this account, ethnicity is not the property of one group, but a relational property.

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